

Preparation and characterization of magnetic nanoparticle encased fluorapatite nanostructure for biomedical applications

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Surface modification of magnetic nanoparticles (MNP) is important in biomedical applications for improving their effective biodistribution, hydrophilicity, colloidal stability, biocompatibility and conjugation of bioactive functional groups. There are numerous organic and inorganic materials used for coating the surface of MNP. The harsh *in vivo* conditions may lead to the disappearance of the organic surface coatings and also the utilization of organic solvent as reagents for generating the organic coatings is a concern from the toxicity point of view. Hence surface modification using inorganic materials may be more effective.

Fluorapatite [FAP, $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6\text{F}_2$] can be a most promising inorganic material for the surface modification of MNP. Surface modification of iron oxide (Fe_3O_4) and zinc ferrite (ZnFe_2O_4) nanoparticles with biocompatible FAP coating achieved by hydrothermal method will be discussed. TEM images revealed MNP encased rod shaped FAP nanoparticles. FAP coated MNP enhanced the cell viability and colloidal stability when compared to MNP. Magnetic measurements of the prepared samples exhibit superparamagnetic nature at room temperature. These results demonstrate that FAP coated MNP could be a suitable candidate for drug delivery, hyperthermia and MRI contrast agent.

Keywords: Magnetic nanoparticles, Fluorapatite, Superparamagnetic